

Beckmann Rearrangement of the Oximes of Some C-Acylcoumarins

R. H. Mehta and Suresh Sethna

Oximes of 5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-, 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-, 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-, and 8-hydroxy-7-acetyl-coumarins afford the corresponding acetamidocoumarin derivatives on the Beckmann rearrangement, using polyphosphoric acid. On hydrolysis of these acetamidocoumarin derivatives, the corresponding aminocoumarins are obtained.

Linch¹ carried out the Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime of 3-acetylcoumarin and obtained 3-aminocoumarin. No other Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime of a C-acylcoumarin appears to have been reported. The present work deals with the Beckmann rearrangement of some C-acylcoumarins in presence of polyphosphoric acid.

Rearrangement of the oximes of 5-hydroxy-6-acetyl- and 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarins furnished 5-hydroxy-6-acetamido- and 7-hydroxy-8-acetamido-4-methylcoumarin respectively. These on hydrolysis afforded 5-hydroxy-6-amino- and 7-hydroxy-8-amino-4-methylcoumarin respectively. Their structures have been established by converting them to the known 5,6-dihydroxy- and 7,8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin^{2,3} by heating them in a sealed tube in nitrogen atmosphere with dilute hydrochloric acid. Mixed m.p. with the authentic samples were not depressed.

Similar rearrangement of the oximes of 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl- and 8-hydroxy-7-acetyl-coumarins furnished 7-hydroxy-6-acetamido-4-methylcoumarin and 8-hydroxy-7-acetamidocoumarin respectively. These on hydrolysis provided 7-hydroxy-6-amino-4-methylcoumarin and 8-hydroxy-7-aminocoumarin, which on direct comparison were found identical with the products obtained on reduction of 7-hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin⁴ and 8-hydroxy-7-nitrocoumarin⁵ with tin and hydrochloric acid. The results indicate that the oximes have *syn*-methyl structures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Oximes.—The acetylcoumarin (6 g.), dissolved in ethanol, was added to a mixture of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (5 g.) and KOH (3 g.). The mixture was stirred vigorously at the room temperature for 1 hr. and then kept overnight. The product separating crystallised from ethanol in needles.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1857.
2. Dalvi *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1951, 28, 366.
3. Fechmann and Duisberg, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119.
4. Shalk and Mehta, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 784.
5. Dey and Kutti, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1940, 6, 641.

7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin required slight heating. The oximes prepared are recorded in Table I.

Beckmann Rearrangement.—The oxime (2 g.) was added to polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 10g. and H_3PO_4 , 6ml). The reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water bath for 3 to 4 hr., protected from moisture. The mixture was cooled to the room temperature and ice-water was added. The product separating, on keeping overnight, crystallised from acetic acid in shining plates. Only in the case of 8-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarin, rearrangement took place at the room temperature. Characteristics of the acetamido derivatives prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Oximes and acetamido derivatives of coumarins.

No	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Nitrogen.		
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
Oximes.									
1.	5-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin	255-56°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$	61.98	61.80	4.87	4.70	5.60	6.00
2.	7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin	259-60°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$	61.42	61.80	4.50	4.70	6.20	6.00
3.	7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin	233-35°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$	61.20	61.80	4.90	4.70	6.40	6.00
4.	8-Hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarin	243-44°	$C_{11}H_9O_4N$	60.02	60.27	4.29	4.10	6.31	6.39
Acetamido derivatives.									
1.	The number	240°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$	61.70	61.80	5.20	4.70	5.74	6.00
2.	corresponds	295-96°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$	61.60	61.80	4.90	4.70	6.10	6.00
3.	to the coumarins	273-75°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$	62.16	61.80	4.60	4.70	6.24	6.00
4.	as above	217-18°	$C_{11}H_9O_4N$	60.07	60.27	4.29	4.10	6.26	6.39

Hydrolysis of the Acetamido Derivative.—The acetamido derivative (2 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with H_2SO_4 (conc., 4ml + 2 ml acetic acid + 2ml water) for 2 hr. This was cooled and neutralised with dilute ammonia. The product separating crystallised from ethanol in shining needles.

7-Hydroxy-6-amino-4-methylcoumarin. — 7-Hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin (0.5 g.) was heated with tin and HCl (conc., 5ml) for 2 hr., cooled to the room temperature, filtered, and neutralised with dilute ammonia. Exhaustive extraction with ether afforded a product, which crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 273-74°.

8-Hydroxy-7-aminocoumarin.—8-Hydroxy-7-nitrocoumarin (0.5 g.) was reduced with tin and HCl (conc.) as in the previous case. The product obtained, on working up as before, was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 199-200°.

TABLE II

Aminocoumarins.

No.	Coumarin.	*M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	5-Hydroxy-6-amino-4-methyl-	262-63°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	62.90	62.80	4.50	4.70	7.00	7.00
2.	7-Hydroxy-6-amino-4-methyl-	273-74°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	63.01	62.90	4.87	4.70	7.20	7.00
3.	7-Hydroxy-8-amino-4-methyl-	275-76°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N	62.70	62.90	4.90	4.70	7.10	7.00
4.	8-Hydroxy-7-amino-	199-200°	C ₉ H ₇ O ₃ N	60.91	61.02	4.05	3.90	7.55	7.90

*The oximes and the amino derivatives start decomposing about 10 to 15° below the m.p. and finally melt at the temperature recorded in the table.

Hydrolysis of the Amino Derivatives.—The aminocoumarin (0.2 g.) was heated in a sealed tube in nitrogen atmosphere with HCl (4 ml) and water (24 ml) at 150-60° for 3 hr. The hydroxycoumarin obtained on ether extraction was crystallised from ethanol in needles. The characteristics and analytical data of the aminocoumarins obtained are recorded in Table II.